

Prediction of weld load resistance using machine learning methods

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ABSTRACT

The article aims to demonstrate how machine learning can be used to estimate the ultimate load resistance of steel welds. At load levels lower than the weld's ultimate load resistance, stress concentrations will often occur along the length of a weld, given by the geometrical configuration of the connected plates and the surrounding structure. For this reason, stress values calculated at lower load levels cannot be used to determine the total weld load resistance directly.

Machine learning methods were therefore used to estimate the weld's ultimate load resistance based on a single given stress state below the weld's ultimate load resistance, assuming a linear increase in all load components. Sufficiently accurate estimates were achieved using convolutional neural networks, and this method was implemented as a part of the Component-based Finite Element Method (CBFEM).

The article also illustrates the advantages and limitations of machine learning methods in the design and assessment of civil structures.

Keywords: machine learning, weld, resistance, steel

1 INTRODUCTION

The Component-based Finite Element Method (CBFEM), which is now a standard tool for the assessment and design of structural steel connections, is based on a combination of the Finite Element Method and the Component Method. One of the main components of the model is the weld component. A special finite element is used to model the behavior of the weld using a nonlinear material model based on the steel plasticity. This approach is consistent with the experiments' results (1). At lower weld load levels, the stress distribution along the weld is non-uniform. At these lower levels, stress peaks occur at the weld. As the weld load increases, there is some utilization of the plastic capacity, the stress peaks gradually smoothen, and the stress is distributed evenly along the weld. In many cases, however, the uneven stiffness of the parts to be joined along the length of the weld must be respected, and the full length of the weld cannot be utilized fully. We speak of a reduced weld length, as described in EN 1993-1-8. This is well illustrated in *Fig. 1*, where the stress peaks approaching the yield stress already occur at 50 % of the weld load capacity. On the right side of *Fig. 1* is the stress state at 100% utilization, where the stress on a significant part of the weld is at the yield point, but the full length of the weld is not fully utilized due to uneven stiffness along the length of the weld. At the same time, the figure illustrates the development of the plastic region. The principle of the CBFEM weld calculation described here has been verified by verification studies (1).

Fig. 1. Stress distribution on the weld at 50% load capacity (left) and at 100% load capacity (right)

Although the CBFEM method is very good at describing the stress-strain behavior of a weld and its load-carrying capacity, it can't be directly used to predict the weld's ultimate load-carrying capacity based on the utilization rate at lower load levels. To reliably determine the ultimate load of a weld, it is necessary to perform the calculation up to the level of this ultimate load, which is generally not practical in engineering practice due to time constraints. A far more common practice is that the connection in the model is loaded with the real value of the load applied to the structure, and it is necessary to assess the real utilization value of a particular weld for its economical design. If, however, the designer had the information that the weld utilization is at 60 %, they could directly reduce its effective size by one-third to increase the weld utilization to 80 %, quickly arriving at a more economical design.

Determining the weld utilization rate for load levels lower than the load capacity of the weld is not straightforward. For example, using the maximum stress value at the weld is inappropriate and very conservative due to the stress peaks, as illustrated in Fig. 1. More advanced utilization estimates based on a combination of the stress value and the strain at the weld have also been used with unsatisfactory results. For these reasons, machine learning methods were employed to predict the actual weld utilization better.

2 CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

Before describing the neural network architecture, the principle of employing convolution filters will be briefly explained. The stress distribution along a weld can be viewed as any other 1D function – a signal of variable length (each weld model can have a different number of elements). The variable number of weld elements in training data is the key reason for implementing convolution. It allows us to look for features or markers through a segment of a given width (a width of 4 in this case) rather than processing whole functions with variable lengths.

Figure 2 illustrates the principle of convolution filters. Consider the stress distribution with values known at 13 points along the weld. The equivalent stress is first normalized to the allowable stress (to account for different material grades used in the training set). Then, two buffer values [(1); (13)] are added (by mirroring the first and the last values) to receive the desired number of output values after convolution. Finally, two different convolution filters (kernels) are presented to serve as an

example, as well as the two respective outputs of convolution. While the first filter smooths the function, the second filter estimates the first derivative of the function. The essence of convolutional neural networks is to employ machine learning methods to find the specific values of these filters so that these filters give meaningful predictions of certain markers and extract latent features (e.g., weighted maxima, values of the maximum first derivative, etc.) that are used for subsequent prediction of the quantity of interest. As illustrated with filter *b*, for example, the first derivative approximation gives us two clear local extremes of the resulting function, highlighting the interval where there are significant differences in stress on neighbouring elements. The problem is, of course, much more complex, so for a deeper study, please refer to the literature, e.g. (2).

Fig. 2. The principle of convolutional filters

3 DESIGN OF A MODEL FOR WELD LOAD CAPACITY PREDICTION

Figure 3 shows the neural network architecture adopted for predicting weld utilization. The inputs taken were the equivalent stress normalized to the allowable stress and the plastic strain normalized to the allowable strain along the weld length. Convolution filters have been applied to these diagrams. Effectively, around 20–40 filters with a width of 4 were used. After applying these filters, maxima are taken from the functions filtered in this way. These maxima were then used as input to a classical neural network with ReLU activation functions. A three-layer neural network with the number of neurons corresponding to twice the number of filters applied in the first two layers and one output neuron proved to be the best training solution. The result of this neural network is a prediction of the weld utilization rate.

Fig. 3. A scheme of a neural network model for predicting weld utilization

Dozens of different weld joint topologies were considered for training (one of the topologies used is shown in *Fig. 1*). Several loading conditions were simulated on each of these topologies, which stressed the weld joint by tension, shear, and combination of actions in various proportions. For each such load condition, a limit load that corresponded to the load capacity of the weld for that combination was found. The calculation was then performed again for lower load levels. In real terms, the calculation was performed in twenty load increments up to the full load capacity of the weld. A stress history along the weld was obtained in each increment corresponding to the already established utilization rate. In this way, thousands of stress curves were obtained for the training of the model described above.

Classical machine learning algorithms were used for training. The mean squared error from the true value was used to evaluate the accuracy of the prediction, achieving a standard deviation value of below 5 %, as shown in *Figure 4*.

Fig. 4. Comparison of actual and predicted weld utilization rates

4 LIMITATIONS AND ADVANTAGES OF USING MACHINE LEARNING METHODS IN STRUCTURAL DESIGN

The presented example of using machine learning methods illustrates both the advantages and limitations of employing these methods in structural design. In particular, these methods should be viewed as advanced statistical methods. The result of the model is not an exact value but rather an estimation of the most probable value with a certain error margin. This is well illustrated in *Figure 5*, which shows the probability distribution of the error in predicting the weld utilization rate by the model described here. This is in direct contrast to the classical exact methods, which are standardly used in structural mechanics. It is important to note that such a model will only be as good as the data provided for training, just as an experienced designer who is able to estimate very well in advance the dimensions of the elements used on a building structure, provided he has encountered and designed similar structures in the past. However, it is always necessary to verify these estimates by calculations.

These models will also always have a limited domain of validity corresponding to the range of data used to train the machine learning model. For example, for this weld utilization rate prediction model. Given the fact that the CBFEM method is used worldwide, it is very likely that this model will

encounter weld topologies that are different from those included in the training set. In such a case, the behavior of this model cannot be predicted with enough precision.

Machine learning models, on the other hand, are capable of dealing with vast amounts of data and are able to predict the behavior of complex systems. In addition, models trained in this way have very fast response times. It is for these reasons that these models will increasingly be used to quickly get to a near-optimal design of certain elements and types of building structures. However, for the foreseeable future, the need to verify this design by classical calculations remains.

Fig. 5. Probability distribution of error and cumulative function of predicted weld utilization rate

5 SUMMARY

In this paper, the use of machine learning methods to predict weld utilization rates was demonstrated. Although a limited set of examples was used to train the model, it is already possible to use it to quickly arrive at an economical design of a large number of weld types and configurations. The training set will be continuously extended with additional examples to achieve higher model reliability.

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